

Colonization and the Form of Violence in Coetzee's Novel *Dusklands*

*Dr. Jamashed Ansari**

*Dr. Aradhana Goswami***

*Implicit in Coetzee's rejection of the realist model is the desire to re-present the acts of violence which constitute a recurring subject in his fiction, without participating in the process of violation which those acts exhibit. Coetzee's renunciation of the realist model also enables him to engage in a second project, one closely associated with the attempt to depict violence without inviting sensationalism. This paper may be as an attempt to counter history as a prison, one in which we are doomed to repeat without difference the contours of a violent past. This past, Coetzee argues, has ensured a present which remains essentially "colonial and is characterised by its inability to sustain itself except through repeated acts of violation". ("Colonialism" 370) Coetzee's first novel, *Dusklands* (1974), demonstrates both thematically and formally these two characteristics of Coetzee's fiction — its awareness of the propensity for a fictional 'treatment' of violence to subvert itself into the form of a fantasy which is pornographic in its effects, and its concern to deconstruct the repetitive structures of colonialism.*

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With *Dusklands* (1974), Coetzee began his "fictional exploration of colonization." ("*Coetzee and Critics*" 17). *Dusklands* investigates the relationships between the colonizer, the historian and the writer of fiction. The work consists of two novellas. The first, "The Vietnam Project," deals with United States' involvement in Vietnam. The narrator of this novella is a mythographer with the ironic name of Eugene Dawn, whose job is to advise the United States military on propaganda strategies aimed at weakening the Vietcong. The book takes its title from the second novella,

* Assistant Professor, Department of English, S. S. S. A. F. Govt. Degree College-Talwari, Tharali, Chamoli, Uttarakhand. Email : jamashedansari@gmail.com

**Assistant Professor, Department of English, Govt. Digvijay Autonomous P.G. College Rajnandgaon, Chhattisgarh. Email : drgoswami197@gmail.com

Dusklands, which consists of two narratives of ‘exploration’ of the South African interior by a Dutch colonist, one said to have taken place in 1760, and one in 1761-62. These ‘explorations’ consist of a series of brutal conquests of the native people of the interior, the Nama. Just as chronological ordering is upset in the narrative of *Dusklands* as a whole by the placement of the Vietnam narrative before the narratives of Dutch colonization, so the later South African exploration is placed before the earlier one. The reversal of chronological order and the juxtaposition of Eugene Dawn, the theorist of conquest, and Jacobus Coetzee [hereafter referred to as Jacobus to avoid confusing Jacobus Coetzee and John Coetzee], the conquistador, suggests that the occupations and preoccupations of these men, though temporally distant from one another, are reciprocally mimetic. Both men are colonizers in a history which repeats itself in the rise and fall of successive empires; both are historians in that they interpret the past using the myth of self and other in its colonial context; and both are revealed, through the various levels of metafiction in their narratives, to be authors of their own fictions.

Eugene Dawn’s narrative is a theory motivated by fantasy, a circumstance which he himself does not recognise. He is identifiable as a type of author not only because writing is a large element of his profession, but also because he corresponds to Coetzee’s description of the author as voyeur (“*Dark Chamber*” 13). Eugene Dawn attempts to enter “the dark chamber” of a Vietnam which he refuses to visit, although he has been given the opportunity to do so. He authorizes his fantasy of penetrating the mythical Vietnam — the one which he creates in his report — by exploiting the form of that report. The fact that his text ‘leaks’ out of that form on either side of the second section in which the report is given, as well as within the so-called report itself, indicates that Eugene Dawn’s perpetual fear has once again been realized. Just as America is unable to subdue the Vietcong, a failure which his report is calculated to overcome, so Eugene Dawn’s fantasy of complete mastery, in this case over his own narrative, is threatened. That the report is consumed by Eugene Dawn’s autobiography is not surprising, for Dawn’s report turns out to be autobiographical once he starts attempting to enact the fantasy which it outlines.

The argument of Dawn’s report is that American propaganda will not be effective firstly until the myth by which it attempts to control the enemy is one with which the Vietnamese are familiar, and

secondly, until the myth used is one which circumvents the ability of the Vietnamese to interpret counterforce as an opportunity to defend their identity, rather than as a radical threat to it. What is needed for America to be victorious, Dawn argues, is not the physical violence of counterforce but cultural violation: the introduction of a countermyth. The voice of the divided self which is the West's heritage from Descartes, and which according to Dawn has been used to little effect in trying to undermine the confidence of the enemy, must be jettisoned in favour of a myth which recognises the Vietnamese privileging of community welfare over the interests of the individual. Eugene Dawn describes the myth that needs to be revised as the Oedipal one of the sons' rebellion against the father. According to him, a form of this myth is prevalent in Vietnamese popular consciousness, and he quotes a (fictional) authority on this point: "The sons of the land (i.e., the brotherhood of earth tillers) desire to take the land (i.e. the Vietnamese *Boden*) for themselves, overthrowing the sky-god who is identified with the old order of power (foreign empire, the U.S.). The earth-mother hides her sons in her bosom, safe from the thunderbolts of the father; at night, while he sleeps, they emerge to unman him and initiate a new fraternal order" (II, pp. 26, 101). (25) According to Dawn, the problem is that within the context of this myth, the father is by definition vulnerable. The father will be repeatedly replaced and overthrown, because the myth of rebellion assumes that heaven and earth, father and mother, live in symbiosis. Neither can exist alone. If the father is overthrown there must be a new father, new rebellion, endless violence, and while no matter how deep her treachery toward her mate, the mother may not be annihilated. The scheming of mother and sons is thus endless. (26) What Dawn proposes instead is the introduction of a father figure, represented by a father-voice on propaganda radio programs, which is presented as invulnerable. The medium of the radio is, according to Dawn, perfectly suited to this message. "Radio information ... is pure authority," he tells us (14), and "the father is authority, infallibility, and ubiquity. He does not persuade, he commands" (21). The success of such propaganda depends, Dawn argues, upon the acknowledgement of the United States' military to themselves that their use of force is not for the purpose of defence, but to demoralize the enemy, because "In limited warfare, defeat is not a military but a psychic concept": ...in practise (sic) our most effective acts of demoralization are justified in military terms, as though the use of force for psychological ends were shameful.

In this scheme the destruction of the protective mother-figure, represented by mother-earth, is crucial. Dawn points out that 'we' no longer live by cultivating the earth, but by decimating 'her,' and that 'we' should recognise that 'we' have forsaken the earth-mother for the goddess of technology, daughter of 'our' own making. Dawn uses the figure of Athene to represent the age of technology: "We have the capacity to breed out of our own head," he states (26). According to Dawn, the capacity of this self-made goddess as saviour needs to be recognised. Thus he reprimands the military for having limited their use of PROP-12, a dramatic soil poison, and for finally discontinuing its use. Such hypocrisy, he argues, is self-defeating: "Until we reveal to ourselves and revel in the true meaning of our acts we will go on suffering the double penalty of guilt and ineffectualness" (29). Eugene Dawn's mythographic prescription for Vietnam can be identified as the fantasy of the sadist, both in terms of Jessica Benjamin's definition of the sadist in *The Bonds of Love* and in the terms of Susan Suleiman's profile of the "'founding' scenario" of the Sadean fantasy in *Subversive Intent: Gender, Politics and the Avant-Garde* (1990) (68). Benjamin defines the sadist as an individual who is incapable of accepting the paradox of mutual independence, in which the need for self-assertion and the need for recognition of the self by another are held in balance. "The sadist perceives dependency on another's recognition of himself as a threat to his independence". (Robbe-Grillet's *novels*, 66) The sadist, then, can receive recognition of his own independence only through violation of another. Since recognition of the self, according to Benjamin, is the source of erotic pleasure, the sadist experiences sexual satisfaction in his violation of another.

In *Dusklands* as a whole, Sadean fantasy operates within the context of colonization, in which it performs as a tool for narrative control. Coetzee's novellas illustrate the use of disguised forms of the Sadean fantasy to justify and perpetuate patterns of domination. This operation is capable of producing a breed of violence which is anything but fantastic. Both Eugene Dawn's fantasy, which masquerades as mythography, and the fantasies of the *Dusklands* novella, which masquerade as history, are narratives that depend upon the Sadean myth to engender the violence of colonization. This violence can be located in the colonist's desire to exclude, to eliminate, that which is other. This 'other' is marked by racial or sexual difference, or by both. The myth that drives the Sadean

fantasy is that this violent exclusion offers its protagonist complete autonomy and absolute power.

Eugene Dawn's narrative shows the Sadean propensity to destroy that which he marks as 'other.' His application of the Oedipus myth to the project of maintaining American superiority over the Vietcong in "The Vietnam Project" indicates collusion between patterns of racial and sexual domination which is evident in his autobiographical 'project' as well. He confesses that he is excited not by sex with Marilyn, his wife, but by three photographs in particular of the many that he carries around with him. These are all photographs which 'celebrate,' as it were, American victories in Vietnam. One is of a large American sergeant copulating with a small Vietnamese woman, who may be a child; the second is of two sergeants, Berry and Wilson, holding the severed heads of three Vietcong; and the third of a prisoner in a tiger cage on Hon Tre Island.

Eugene Dawn's excitement at scenes of domination and his obsessive desire for absolute control are mirrored in the actions of Jacobus Coetzee. In this respect, Jacobus represents the fulfilment of Eugene Dawn's fantasy, for Jacobus is the Sadean hero victorious. Jacobus views the territories of both the native and the female in the same way. To him they represent only opportunities for mastery, areas for colonization. Just as Dawn is excited to the pitch of erotic fantasy by the photographs illustrating mastery, Jacobus tells us that the ideal condition for stimulating his erotic pleasure is rape. His ideal sex-object embodies the violation of a figure who represents both sexual and racial difference: a Bushman girl. Sex with Dutch girls affords no pleasure, Jacobus tells us, because Dutch girls embody property and therefore power, and are in this respect inviolable. Bushmen girls, on the other hand, can be used and left for dead. With a Dutch girl you lose your freedom....Whereas a wild Bushman girl is tied into nothing, literally nothing. She may be alive but she is as good as dead. She has seen you kill the men that represented power to her; she has seen them shot down like dogs. You have become power itself now and she nothing, a rag you wipe yourself on and throw away.... She can kick and scream but she knows she is lost That is the freedom she offers, the freedom of the abandoned.... She has given up the ghost; she is flooded in its stead with your will. Her response to you is absolutely congruent with your will. She is the ultimate love you have bome [,] your own desires

alienated in a foreign body and pegged out waiting for your pleasure. (61)

What remains to be investigated is that even more complex feature of the fantasies of domination and submission in *Dusklands*, namely their masochistic element. If Dawn and Jacobus constantly seek confrontations from which they may gain sadistic forms of self-recognition, it is perhaps not surprising that these figures also illustrate the propensity for reversal between sadistic and masochistic components which Jessica Benjamin has identified as characteristic of the sadomasochistic relationship. Sadism and masochism, Benjamin has argued, are two sides of the same coin in that both are bids for recognition of the self. In masochism, this desire for self-acknowledgement expresses itself paradoxically, in the submission of the self to a dominant other's will, in an attempt to gain at least a vicarious independence. Both Eugene Dawn and Jacobus Coetzee's fantasies of confrontation with an other, while they provide instances for occupation and therefore sadistic recognition, are also described in ways that suggest that Dawn and Jacobus also experience the masochist's desire to be 'occupied,' or in Benjamin's vocabulary, to be "reached, penetrated, found, released" (73). Thus there is a paradoxical disappointment on the part of Dawn and Jacobus Coetzee when the enemy — be it Vietcong or Bushman or even occasionally woman--- fails to be dominant, fails to represent an appropriate resistance to the will of the colonizer. This disappointment lies in the failure of the enemy to provide the Americans (in the case of Dawn) and the whites (in the case of Jacobus Coetzee) with an opportunity for masochistic self-recognition through surrender.

The desire for absolute mastery which the gun represents takes in this instance its sadistic form: Jacobus receives self-gratification from the destruction of all that he determines to be other. In a reversal of sadistic and masochistic bids for recognition, the reversal which Benjamin identifies as characteristic of sadomasochistic relationships, the desire for absolute mastery also takes a masochistic form. In this case evidence of aggression inflicted upon the self is desired for its potential to be interpreted as self-recognition. This desire expresses itself as the perverse wish to be 'shot,' to be victim rather than victorious. Eugene Dawn's 'history' of the American-Vietcong encounter reflects this desire. In it he refers to both colonization and rape as opportunities for masochistic self-recognition in which the 'enemy' has failed America by proving itself to be vulnerable in the case of the fighters, and to be

unresponsive (at least in the desired fashion) in the case of the women. The 'failure' of the enemy lies in its unsuitability as an idol to command masochistic submission on the part of the invaders: "We brought them (the Vietcong] our pitiable selves," Eugene Dawn tells us,

The points in the text where there exists the largest propensity for the narrator to perform as sadist, and the reader to respond as masochist are those which represent violence. Here in particular Coetzee takes care to mark the scenes of violence as *representations* of violence. Both the Vietnam photographs (the fact that they are photographs clearly indicates that this is a 'frame-up') and the orgies of sadistic violence in which Jacobus indulges, display what Debra Castillo, using a Barthesian term, labels an "'overconstructed horror' ... that prohibits empathy" — the empathy necessary for a reading of these scenes to be pornographic. Thus Coetzee's narrative does not encourage the reader's involvement as participant in pornography of violence, but rather points the reader to the fact that the violence which he represents lies *elsewhere*. Castillo's reading of the metafictional aspect of the photographs demonstrates this strategy: J. M. Coetzee's primary purpose in providing shock photos of an untenable reality is to release the silenced, unimaginable other, the pictorial 'ghosts or absences,' of themselves from the spectacle of horror that imprisons them (*Dusklands* 17)... The fictive surface, yielding to penetration as the tiger cage does not, releases lacerating horror, bruising the reader, who can, finally, *feel* the point that description alone cannot provide, releasing her into a vigilance through or beyond the text. ("*Mythic Punctum*" 1114)

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